

Ageing@Work

Smart, Personalized and Adaptive ICT Solutions for Active, Healthy and Productive Ageing with enhanced Workability

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Executive Summary

This document describes the components and technologies of the Ageing@Work system. The aim is to provide an extended overview of the different blocks and components described in the technical deliverables, illustrating how these components interact as a unique system and how they provide the different functionalities that will be validated into the pilots. As result of that an overview of the different demonstrators deployed in the pilot sites are presented in this deliverable, their main functionalities and how the different components required to interact to provide global functionalities of the system. This deliverable complements the D7.4 Ageing@Work Integrated System demonstrator

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List of Terms and definitions

Abbreviation	Definition
wVUMs	Worker Virtual user model
AVC	Ambient Virtual Coach
VR/AR	Virtual/Augmented reality
D	Deliverable
A@W	Ageing@Work
GFC	General Functional Component
KEP	Knowledge Exchange Platform
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
AAR	Android Archive Library
SDK	Software Development Kit
API	Application Programming interface

Table 1 Definitions

1. Introduction

The Ageing@Work system is aimed at providing support to the aging worker, both at home and at work while enabling a flexible connection of these two main daily aspects of the workers' life and their balance. It is important to remind the main objectives of the project:

- Enable extensive personalization capabilities to the Ageing@Work supportive approach:
 - Developing the worker Virtual User Models (wVUMs) to encode worker specificities
 - Personalization of the tools offered by the system
 - Personalized predictive assessment of worker state and trends
 - Personalized suggestions on work ergonomics, scheduling healthy activities (such physical activities or leisure activities) and well-being factors
- Novel unobtrusive worker activity and behaviour monitoring framework to acquire ample understanding of the workers' activities of interest and behavioural factors, both at work and beyond, with special emphasis on unobtrusiveness, data privacy and security.
- Provide workers with personalized work ergonomics and process design services, so they can adapt workplace physical design and their task assignments and scheduling.
- Provide with an Ambient Virtual Coach (AVC) to encompass the work and life support capabilities of the system
- Development of three core tools to increase productivity and workability based on Virtual and Augmented reality (VR/AR) and Visual analytics
 - AR and VR telepresence tool
 - Personalized VR and AR based lifelong training tool
 - Knowledge sharing and collaboration platform

The content of the document represents a first step towards the achievement of the objectives. The development and experimentation will verify the validity of the technical choice made in during the co-design and will proof the system feasibility.

1.1 Scope of the deliverable

This deliverable is intended for public dissemination and provide a synthesis of the deliverables D3.2, D3.3, D4.1, D4.2, D5.1, D5.2, D5.3, D6.1, D6.2, D6.3, D6.4 and D6.5 describing the specification of the Ageing@Work tools and services. This deliverable also complements the deliverable D7.4 providing the required documentation to understand demonstrator main working functionalities.

1.2 Relation to other activities and deliverables

This deliverable summarizes the work done in WP3-WP6 during the project execution and demonstrates the development activities in those WPs as well as the description of the inter-workpackages interactions for successfully deploy the final Ageing@Work system. This deliverable complements D2.7 system architecture description with the final implementation of the envisioned components and also D7.4, that

is the real-life demonstrator of the components and services described in the present document. Finally, the feasibility of the system presented in D7.1 (and D7.4) will be demonstrated within the activities of validation in the WP7 and the results are planned to be presented in D7.3 at the end of the pilots.

2. Overview of the Ageing@Work integration methodology

This section presents the overall strategy to develop the different components included in the Ageing@System and to integrate them into a fully functional system that covers the objectives presented in the introduction of this document.

2.1 Overview of the Ageing@Work system

The Ageing@Work system is built on a set of interrelated components based on open technology standards and global technology interoperability techniques. Figure 1 presents the main components and their relationship.

From them, the Ambient Activity and Behaviour Tracking Tool (see section 4.1.3) integrates mobile devices and other sensors to collect data from users and their environments. This component gather data from the workers' activities and based on these data, other components can personalize the workers' services they offer. Together with this, the Centralized Repository (section 3.1) is responsible for storing the collected data set. This component, together with the Ageing@Work API enables data and services sharing between system components.

Productivity Enhancement tools composed by the AR Situational Awareness Tool (section 4.2.2), the AR telepresence tool (section 4.2.3), the Ageing@Work Knowledge Sharing Tool (section 4.2.4) and the VR/AR lifelong learning tools (section 4.2.1) provide support access to the knowledge base and learning resources to the workers.

The Worker Dashboard (section 4.1.2) and the Virtual Coach (4.1.4) are the main components that provide daily assistance to the workers through their mobile phone using multimodal communication.

In addition to these main tools and services: the Reward System provides a gamification engine to can be adapted to improve the workers adherence to a specific objective (section 4.4.1) and the Ergonomics Optimization Support Tools (section 4.4.2) simulates the ergonomic assessment of the workplace so workers become aware of their workplace ergonomic status.

Finally, these workers tools and services are complemented by the Management/Expert Platform (see section 4.3) that provides managers with a set of tools for visualizing the available data and interaction with each worker management tool.

More information about the Ageing@Work system architecture can be found in the D2.8 Ageing@Work System Architecture-V2.

Figure 1 Overview of the technical architecture of Ageing@Work with the different components and the WPs involved in the development

2.2 Ageing@Work integration methodology

The integration methodology followed by Ageing@Work was agreed at the beginning of the project, during the design phase, with the objective of facilitating the continuous integration process as well as guarantee the final quality of the individual software components before the final integration process. This section presents a summary of the Integration Plan agreed in M6 internally.

The objective of the Integration plan was to provide a common validation methodology that ensures the necessary quality in the different Ageing@Work subcomponents that facilitate the delivery of the Ageing@Work system at the end of the project.

Following the ISO/IEC 2510:2011 system/software quality model characteristics, the Ageing@Work Integration methodology will be conducted in three main steps:

- 1) Integration at subcomponent level. Each of the architectural submodules in the Figure 1 will be integrated at partner level
- 2) Integration at General Functional component (GFC) level. Each of the subcomponents are part of a GFC described in the previous section, with a responsible who will coordinate the different GFC releases
- 3) Integration at Ageing@Work final platform. The GFC responsible collaborate to provide the whole integrated platform.

In each of the steps, the partners involved in the development will conduct the technical validation of the components in order to guarantee the successful integration of the different Subcomponents in to the GFC and the GFC into the integrated Ageing@Work system. The technical validation will include the assessment of the subcomponent documentation and it will be referred in the corresponding deliverable describing the component development.

2.2.1 Definition of roles and metrics

The integration was divided in 7 main modules according to the architecture description (Table 2):

Table 2 Main Architectural components and responsible Partners for integration plan deployment in each component

GFC/integration responsible	Subcomponent	Sub Respon
GFC1 Ageing@Work Mobile app Responsible: CERTH	Virtual Coach Cognition T5.4	CERTH
	User’s Emotions Mirroring T5.1	UPAT, CERTH
	UI: Text-to-Speech T5.1	CERTH
	UI: Speech-to-Text T5.1	CERTH
	UI: Lip Sync T5.1	CERTH
	UI: Gesture Recognition T5.1 & T5.4	CERTH
	Worker Dashboard T5.2	UPM
GFC2 Ambient Activity & Behaviour Tracking Responsible: CERTH	Reward System Widgets T5.3	SAMSUNG
	Affective Traits Monitoring T4.3	UPAT
	Worker Activity & Behaviour Monitoring T4.2	CERTH
	Online User Activity Monitoring T4.2	CERTH
GFC3 Productivity enhancement tools Responsible: UPAT	eSurveys T4.2	CERTH
	Encryption, Authentication, Security T4.4	CERTH
	AR Telepresence Tools T6.4	CERTH
	AR Situational Awareness Tools T6.1	CERTH
GFC4 Manager/Expert Platform Responsible: CERTH	VR and AR Life Long Learning Tools T6.2	UPAT
	Knowledge sharing tools T6.3	UPAT
	Participatory Work Orchestration Optimization Support Tool T3.5	HIT
	Management Dashboard T3.5	CERTH
	Visual Analytics T3.5	CERTH
GFC5 Ergonomics Optimization Support Tool Responsible: MYSPHERA	Optimization Algorithms T3.5	HIT
	Data Aggregation Tool T5.5	CERTH
GFC6 Reward System (Gamification Engine) Responsible: SAMSUNG	3D Simulator T3.4	MYSPHERA
	Simulation Testing Report Generator T3.4	MYSPHERA
GFC7 Ageing@Work Centralized Repository Responsible: UPAT	Rule-Based Engine T5.3	SAMSUNG
	Manager’s Dashboard T5.3	SAMSUNG
	Reward System API T5.3	SAMSUNG
GFC7 Ageing@Work Centralized Repository Responsible: UPAT	Knowledgebase: AR &VR Scenario T6.2	CERTH
	Knowledgebase: Search Engine T6.2	UPAT
	Virtual Worker Models T3.2	CERTH

3. Core components for integration

3.1 Ageing@Work Central Repository

The main information hub of the Ageing@Work system is the Central repository. Every of the components in the system securely share and exploit the information from other modules and components through the services provided by the Central Repository, including the Virtual Worker Model and the Virtual Workplace Model. At high level the Central Repository is a MongoDB database, storing information in JSON style documents, based on the Open API Specification (<https://api.ageing.iti.gr/api/documentation>) through REST APIs (as described in D3.2). The API capabilities include storing and retrieving new information. Detailed information of the Central Repository and the Ageing@Work API is included in the D2.8 Ageing@Work system architecture. The following figure presents visually a summary of the main feature of the Ageing@Work Central Repository.

Figure 2 Main features of the Ageing@Work Central Repository

4. Demonstrators

In order to demonstrate the usefulness and feasibility of the Ageing@Work system, different demonstrators based on the defined use cases have been deployed along the pilot sites. The objective of these demonstrators is to provide a real-life working environment of the Ageing@Work integrated tools while collecting information and evidence of the working performance of the deployed tools and services. In order to facilitate the understanding of the functionalities of the system, three different demonstrators have been deployed in the pilot sites, attending different conditions of the involved workers.

The final three demonstrators are: the Worker app with the full functionalities of the Virtual Coach and the Dashboard, the Productivity Enhancement tools with the different AR/VR tools and Knowledge Exchange Platform and the Management/Expert Platform with the dashboard for Job scheduling tools. More information about the planned use cases is reported in D2.2. further information about the use case and demonstrators’ deployment within the pilot sites is reported in D7.2. Updated videos with the last releases of the demonstrators will be also published in the [YouTube Ageing@Work project channel](#).

4.1 Ageing@Work Worker application

The Ageing@Work application is an Android app that will be fully piloted in Spanish pilot site with 40 workers in different quarries and associated installations such laboratories.

4.1.1 General architecture

The Ageing@Work Worker applications is comprised by three main components as it is shown in Figure 3: The Worker Dashboard, the Virtual Coach and the tracking services. While the Worker Dashboard and the Virtual Coach offered the main interaction component to the workers, the tracking services are totally transparent for them.

Figure 3 Worker Mobile app high level architecture

4.1.2 Worker Dashboard

This section will explain the integrations of the Worker Dashboard with other sections. The Worker Dashboard, as has been explained in the deliverable D5.1, is composed by 4 main modules. Each of these modules has a basic function and groups all the related content to allow users to access information more efficiently. The modules are (Figure 4):

- My Messages: for Ageing@work communication between system tools and workers.

- My daily habits: for providing self-awareness of the three main areas for a successful ageing in terms of physical, social and mental health.
- My job: show results of workability questionnaires and ergonomic evaluations.
- My goals: to know if the goals are balanced to achieve personalized objectives in the physical, sleep and leisure/social domains.

Figure 4. Main page of the Worker Dashboard

My messages module shows the notifications and messages received by the user. In this case, the type of message is collected from the backend service (in the Ageing@Work API), in order to classify it, the content of the message and the date on which it was issued is gathered. Finally, the status is also retrieved, which can be read or pending to read. The user can mark a message as read or even delete it. This information is

sent to the backend to update its status. To collect all the data and integrate the Worker Dashboard with the different project systems, the Ageing@Work API. To integrate the messages into the Worker Dashboard, a method in the Central Repository API is used to retrieve the data from the Ageing@Work Central Repository. In order to update the status of the notifications or messages and inform the Virtual Coach the API method (system_notification/read/ + id of the notification) has been used.

The information displayed in the My work module (Figure 5) basically collects from the backend the results of the ergonomics evaluation of the workplace, the responses to the workability assessment and recommendations based on the number of work breaks provided. The results of the ergonomic evaluation are integrated, through the Ageing@Work API, of the ergonomic optimization support tool system of the project. The data is a JSON that contains the type of each element of the workplace evaluated, the best configuration of this element to ensure good ergonomics at work. Only those parameters that the user can adjust in their workstation will be shown, such as the height of the chair or table.

Figure 5 Main screen of the Ergonomic module

Also, as in the rest of the cases, to retrieve the information from the workability assessment carried out by users through the Ageing@Work Worker application, a method of the Ageig@Work API has been used. The API response includes an array with the responses of the last 7 days to each of the questions of the

dedicated workability self-assessment test, the date and the value of the scale. Finally, the number of recommended work breaks collected according the VUM data is presented in the section. It also shows a message encouraging to meet the objective, or if it is not adequate to readjust it.

The My goals module (Figure 6) retrieves the goal of steps and minutes of daily activity, data composed of the type and value of the goal using the API (/ data / goals / latest). With the information collected, the Worker Dashboard gives advice on the need to meet the objectives to have a healthy life, and if the values are not adjusted to the real pattern of the worker (using a colour code (green, yellow or red)) and a message informs the user of the need to change the objective to one more recommended by the experts (Figure 7).

Figure 6 My goals section of the Worker Dashboard

Adults should:

- aim to be physically active every day. Any activity is better than none, and more is better still
- do strengthening activities that work all the major muscles (legs, hips, back abdomen, chest, shoulders and arms) on at least 2 days a week
- do at least 150 minutes of moderate intensity activity a week or 75 minutes of vigorous intensity activity a week
- reduce time spent sitting or lying down and break up long periods of not moving with some activity
- the recommended amount of sleep for a healthy adult is at least seven hours

Figure 7 My goals section recommendations

In the module of my daily objectives, the summary of the activity and sleep and leisure time of the last day are shown in the first tab, which are the data that is shown in more detail in the following 3 tabs respectively. This summary was obtained by calling the API (/ steps / from / '+' startDate + "/" to /" + endDate) for the steps, the API call (/ sleep / from /' + startDate + "/" to / "+ endDate) for the sleep data and finally the method (/ leisure / from / '+' startDate + "/" to / "+ endDate) for the leisure time information. In all cases, the startDate and endDate parameters refer to the dates from which the data is to be obtained.

4.1.3 Ambient activity and behaviour tracking

In this section, the components related to the activity and behaviour tracking will be briefly described. Each component was described thoroughly in the D4.1 “Unobtrusive ambient activity and behaviour tracking” and the pipelines connecting the individual components were presented. Since then, within the D4.2 “Worker behaviour & affective traits monitoring methods & infrastructure”, the architectural and component updates were reported. In Table 3, all the individual components related to the activity and behaviour tracking are described.

Table 3 Activity and behaviour tracking integrated components

Name	Data	Details	Integration Type
Location Tracking Library	Latitude, Longitude, Address	Uses cellular network or GPS. Methods for geocoding and battery optimizations	Android Archive Library (AAR)
Activity Tracking Library	Google Activity Recognition: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Walking, Still, Running, In Vehicle, On Bicycle, Tilting CNN model: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Walking, Still, Upstairs, Downstairs Step Counter: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Steps, Activity Intensity, Calories, METs 	Googles Activity Recognition: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Orientation/Position independent. Battery optimization implemented. CNN based on UCI HAR dataset: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Orientation/Position depended. Battery restricted. Step Counter: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provides step counting updates every few seconds. 	AAR
Location Context API	Locations Category and Subcategory	Custom API that uses OpenStreetMap's files to categorize locations.	Dedicated Dockerized service
Generic Phone Usage Tracking Library	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Charging Events, Battery Levels • Connectivity (Wifi) events • Phone calls (duration, timestamp, anonymized, SHA-256, caller id) • Screen on/off events 	Listener service that tracks generic phone usage data.	AAR
Keyboard	Press/Release Time, Distance, Deletion	Uses AOSP keyboard files modified to record keystroke Time Sequences.	AAR
Self-Reports	Demographics, Questionnaires	Users are prompted to answer self-administered questionnaires periodically and demographic related questions.	Integrated within the application's UI. Retrieves questionnaires from the VUM server through HTTP requests.
Samsung Accessory SDK	Raw data: Accelerometer, Gyroscope, Heart rate	Provides methods for raw data retrieval from Samsung Smartwatches.	Software Development Kits (SDK)
Samsung Health SDK	Steps, Water intake, Activities, Floors Climbed, Heart rate, Sleep stages	Provides various health / activity related data while using Samsung phone or smartwatch.	SDK
Google Fit	Steps, Sleep Metrics, Activities, Heart rate	Provides various health / activity related data while using an Android phone.	SDK/ External API
Clinical Platform API	Weight, Humidity, Luminescence,	Receives IoT derived data and store them under strict protocols.	Dedicated Server/Service.

	Temperature, Blood pressure, Blood Glucose, Questionnaires	Offers data visualization over aggregated periods and management tools for the administration (e.g. add new Questionnaires).	Rest communication
Virtual User Model Server (VUM)	Provides: Login credentials Stores: All the data above	All the above data, collected by the middleware, are stored on an SQLite database inside the phone. Periodically, if Wi-Fi is available, these data are sent to VUM. Additionally, methods for a notification broadcast system are provided.	Dedicated Server/ Rest communication

We can categorize their integration type within 4 groups.

- The Android Archive Library (AAR), which consists of native Android code formatted into an independent library, able to be imported as a single file within the main project. When imported all its public functions can be used without any additional overhead.
- The Software Development Kits (SDK), similarly to the AAR, are independent libraries which are able to be imported through configuration files within the main project. They are being downloaded over specific repositories and are mostly considering third party services or interconnection with other applications. Usually, additional code is needed to be written in order to wrap the SDKs functionality and connected with the rest of the system.
- The external Application Programming Interface (API), which are used to communicate with external services or applications. The communication is based on Restful logic using the HTTP protocol.
- The dedicated server/services, which are communicating with the main application using Restful logic through HTTP requests. This category mostly refers to services provided by the Ageing@Work dedicated server.

The components above can be unified and used in parallel within the Ageing@Work application. For example, under the behavioural tracking component/service the Location and Activity tracking libraries are being used in combination to receive the information of both location and activities. This information is then translated to contextualized behaviour aspects (e.g., Worker is “sitting” (activity) at “work” (location) for 60 minutes) which can trigger suggestive wellbeing events through the Virtual Coach or notifications. Workers can configure aspects of the behavioural tracking component within the app and provide their home and work addresses (Figure 8 and Figure 9).

Figure 8 Continuous behavioural tracking

Figure 9 Tracking configuration

Since the main application is written in Ionic, the Android libraries and services are interconnected using Cordova. Cordova acts like a bridge between the Angular methods and Android ones. Anything that needs to be running all the time, like the activity & location tracking services, needs to be written in native Android while on the other hand the frontend of the application is written in Angular (JavaScript/TypeScript/HTML/CSS). That means that whenever the UI needs to activate a functionality or retrieve data from the backend, we need a bridge using Cordova, as to connect the frontend with the backend. This bridge usually consists of well-defined functions that are mapping JavaScript functions to native Android ones, while also providing methods to transfer data between the two.

In order to debug the backend of the application and the eventful logic of the activity & behavioural tracking logging methods were used, which outputted the logging information through the Android Studio. Additionally, methods were created to test and ensure the desired functionality of various methods and to test corner cases. Furthermore, emulated devices were used in order to test the location related event's functionality (Android studio's emulator allows us to change the emulated device's location). Finally, and most importantly, the application has been used in real life settings for many months with many iterations of bug fixes and improvements, to reach a crash free state even after continuous usage for several months.

4.1.4 Avatar Virtual Coach

In this section the integration of the Avatar Virtual Coach (AVC) will be described. The AVC is a core component of the Ageing@Work application which communicates the system's messages with the users in a more direct and life-like method. The AVC 3D models were initially created in the Character Creator program and then were imported in Unity. The development tools used to create the avatar were reported in depth in D5.1 "Ageing@Work mirroring avatar and ageing Worker Dashboard". The functionalities of the avatar, such as the Text to speech mechanism, were written in Unity and then were built as a separate Android project. This project files were used in order to port the avatar within the main application.

Figure 10 Avatar Virtual Coach 3D models

Within the main application a Java package with methods calling the appearance of the avatar, as well as the 3D assets, are ported. The avatar is being held within a fragment Android View, as to consume only a segment of the viewport. As with all the other Android methods, the avatar's backend functionality is interconnected with the application's frontend using Cordova as a bridge. Whenever the avatar is needed to read a Text to Speech message, which was originated by the Behavioral tracking component, the pipeline is the following (Figure 11).

1. From the Behavioral tracking component, where location and activity tracking are performed, an event triggers a wellbeing suggestion.
2. This suggestion's text is first outputted as a notification.
3. When the user opens the application, the Ionic (Angular) frontend requests from the Android backend, through the Cordova bridge, the latest avatar message. The Android backend retrieves this message from the SQLite database within the application and returns it to the front end.

4. The received message is then transferred from the Ionic frontend, through which the Avatar appearance and communication bridge was initialized, to the Avatar's android backend.
5. There, native methods are being called in order to perform Text to Speech conversion and at the same time the Unity functions are enabled to simulate the lips and body movement.

Figure 11 Integrated Avatar Virtual Coach

4.2 AR/VR tools and Knowledge Exchange Platform

4.2.1 General architecture

This group of components aims to enhance the productivity and workability of the worker using different bidirectional communications and services based on AR/VR for helping workers learn new tasks and skills. The high-level architecture is shown in the following figure

Figure 12 The architecture of the AR/VR tools and Knowledge Exchange Platform

4.2.2 AR situational awareness tool

The goal of the AR situational awareness tool is to develop smart visualizations allowing the intuitive display of notifications which make the worker aware of the work tasks in progress. Activities in this task are reported in D6.1. The main focus of this tool has been to provide an AR-enhanced environment for the worker, by using video feed from a smartphone camera which is then given as input to the object detection and tracking algorithm. Then, the outline and 3D pose of objects of interest on the workspace, are displayed on the screen, and a series of intuitive steps are shown to guide the worker in the execution of a specific work task.

To demonstrate the functionality of this tool, we have deployed two scenarios: one for the AR guidance of workers on the use of a 3D printer, and another on workers' guidance in using properly a drilling machine. Both scenarios utilise equipment which is actually being used by workers in the premises of SIEMENS.

Below, we illustrate the steps required for the worker to use the AR situational awareness tool for the case of using the 3D printer (in a similar fashion, the scenario of using the drilling machine has also been implemented):

1. User points the smartphone towards the printer
2. Printer is registered in AR using embedded logo as tag
3. Steps are displayed on smartphone screen
4. Relevant printer features (e.g. controls or components) are annotated on screen as shown in the below figure

Figure 13 AR Situation Awareness Tool: Steps and AR annotations displayed on smartphone screen to guide worker on the use of a 3D printer at his workplace

The tool was developed with Unity3D. A video demonstrating the functionality of the tool is available at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=TWMZ7M5US0Y>.

4.2.3 AR Telepresence tool

The goal of the AR telepresence tool is to support remote collaboration of workers through AR technology, toward increasing autonomy and flexibility for workers and enhancing their productivity. Details on this tool are provided in D6.3. More specifically, the AR telepresence tool provides real-time communication among workers, offering work collaboration possibilities anytime-anywhere.

The tool offers bi-directional real-time communication (video stream, voice chat) and AR annotation transfer between remote and on-site workers, who can use either their smartphones or a head-mounted Microsoft HoloLens device. The remote expert can insert various annotations on a captured frame to guide the on-site worker (pointing arrows, 3D Text, 3D animations (e.g., hand pushing button)). The annotations then appear as 3D models superimposed over the real objects in the on-site worker's field of view (Figure 14).

Figure 14 Left: Worker using the AR Telepresence Tool - The remote worker inserts an AR annotation (red arrow) in real-time to guide the on-site worker on the execution of a specific task, Right: The onsite worker can use either a

phone or a head-mounted Hololens device to view the annotations sent by the remote worker and complete a specific task

The tool offers recording of log files with the performed actions in JSON format, by exploiting the wVUM communication capabilities and storing them in the Aging@Work infrastructure. Each action (e.g., login into a remote collaboration session, use of AR annotation “arrow”, deletion of an annotation, etc.) is defined by its type and a timestamp. Analysis of the acquired data collections offers the ability to examine the usability and efficiency of the tool within the envisaged pilots.

Furthermore, the tool has been integrated with the manager platform, so that managers are enabled to

Figure 15 The manager can schedule an AR remote collaboration session through the manager platform

Figure 16 Notification to worker for a scheduled AR remote collaboration session

schedule AR remote collaboration sessions (date, time, and workers to collaborate) between two workers as shown in the Figure 16. Then, the workers receive notification about their scheduled session on the determined time. The tool was developed with Unity3D and the API functionality has been tested with standardized API calls using Postman. Furthermore, usability testing of the tool has been performed with one SIEMENS worker, as well as testing with other 8 workers at CERTH. The usability score was 94% measured with the System Usability Scale (SUS), thereby demonstrating excellent usability. Videos demonstrating the functionality of the tool are available at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=5xvdDpGLOnM>, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Pf9dX98j3lY>. The tool has also been publicly published as an Android app in the Google Playstore (as shown by the figure below).

Figure 17 AR Telepresence Tool publicly published in Google Playstore

4.2.4 Ageing@Work knowledge sharing

In this section, the integration of the Knowledge Exchange Platform (KEP) is briefly described. Activities in this task follow the work performed in T6.3 on knowledge sharing which is reported in deliverable D6.2. The main goal of the KEP is to provide a fully informative forum that will empower workers in the manufacturing industry, especially the experienced older workers who become more important as “knowledge providers”. The aim is to develop an engaging solution for knowledge sharing and learning benefitting both on site and remote work, that will improve work well-being and create a safer and healthier work environment. As a result, motivation and hence productivity is expected to increase, leading to a global benefit for the working community.

The need for engaging knowledge sharing frameworks becomes more important when problems occur, or workers need to share their hands-on knowledge/experience and cooperate with others. These days, with the effects of the global pandemic (COVID-19) affecting all working aspects, information flow among the working environment has been severely deteriorated. Aforementioned factors led us to the conclusion that easy access to knowledge could improve the efficiency of production, providing workers with information easily, that will improve both performance and satisfaction.

KEP Presentation and required steps

A user can connect to the platform with a personal profile. To create a profile the user is requested to provide his/her credentials (email - password authentication) and choose a username for the platform (Figure 18).

The screenshot shows the registration interface for Ageing@Work. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the Ageing@Work logo, a menu icon, a flame icon, a clock icon, a group of people icon, and a search icon. On the right side of the navigation bar are the links 'Register' and 'Login'. Below the navigation bar, the breadcrumb 'Home / Register' is displayed. The registration form consists of the following elements:

- Email address:** A text input field with the placeholder text 'Enter a valid email address' and a small icon on the right.
- Username:** A text input field with the placeholder text 'Enter your username'.
- Password:** A text input field with the placeholder text 'Enter your password' and a small icon on the right. Below this field, a note states: 'Your password's length must be at least 6 characters.'
- Confirm Password:** A text input field with the placeholder text 'Confirm your password' and a small icon on the right.
- reCAPTCHA:** A checkbox labeled 'I'm not a robot' next to the reCAPTCHA logo and the text 'reCAPTCHA Privacy - Terms'.
- Register Now:** A teal button with the text 'Register Now'.

Figure 18 KEP register window preview

Once connected, the worker has the ability to see all the categories listed in the KEP forum. This window is used as the home screen for the Ageing@Work project. The navigation menu items are shown on the top of Figure 19.

Figure 19 Categories/Home window preview and navigation menu items

The default categories we have already listed for the prototype version of the project comprises four distinct sections:

- **Instructions**, which act as a welcoming section especially for new users/workers,
- **3D Models** category
- a **Tutorials** section which can be used to upload zip files with models or even tutorial steps, as json formatted files and
- **Manuals** section, that has been mostly populated with general data at this time (e.g tele-cooperation help for workers, exercises to warm up etc.).

Content is organized in Categories > Topics > Posts easing organization and navigation for the users. Users can decide which topic to follow based on views and individual posts, each category possesses a process that can speed up his information retrieval.

Users that can view this post can reply by composing a new form, filled with text or other multimedia mentioned beforehand. An example of a post is shown in Figure 20. The option to indicate “like” at posts is also considered, so that workers can upvote documents or posts they found helpful. In general, enabling workers to interact and share contextually relevant knowledge, ideas and good practices was our main goal for this forum.

VR software Guide

Stefanos

Monday, 27 September 2021

Oculus:

You can download the Oculus software in this [link](#).

Hardware Specs:

Component	Recommended Specs	Minimum Specs
Processor	Intel i5-4590 / AMD Ryzen 5 1500X or greater	Intel i3-6100 / AMD Ryzen 3 1200, FX4350 or greater
Graphics Card	NVIDIA GTX 1060 / AMD Radeon RX 480 or greater	NVIDIA GTX 1050 Ti / AMD Radeon RX 470 or greater
Alternative Graphics Card	NVIDIA GTX 970 / AMD Radeon R9 290 or greater	NVIDIA GTX 960 4GB / AMD Radeon R9 290 or greater
Memory	8GB+ RAM	8GB+ RAM
Operating System	Windows 10	Windows 10
USB Ports Rift	3x USB 3.0 ports, plus 1x USB 2.0 port	1x USB 3.0 port, plus 2x USB 2.0 ports
Video Output (Rift)	Compatible HDMI 1.3 video output	Compatible HDMI 1.3 video output

HTC Vive:

You can download the Oculus software in this [link](#).

Hardware Specs:

Specifications	Minimum system requirements
Computer type	Desktop computer with available PCIe slot
Processor	Intel Core i5-4590/AMD FX 8350 equivalent or better
GPU	NVIDIA GeForce GTX 1060, AMD Radeon R9 480 equivalent or better
Memory	4 GB RAM or more (8 GB RAM is recommended)
Operating system	64-bit Windows 10 or Windows 7 SP1
SteamVR app	Version 1533664367 or later

Valve Index:

You can download the SteamVR software in this [link](#), after running the [performance check](#) to check if your PC meets the recommended specifications

[Login to reply](#) 0

Figure 20 Example of a Post inside a category

A user, on click, can view categories section, popular topics, recent posts made by other workers and access the searching tool (Figure 21). All these menu items aim at proper navigation and convenient experience.

Topic Title:

File Edit View Insert Format

↶ ↷
B
I
U

PDF
XR tutorial
ZIP file

...

POWERED BY TINY

Close
Submit

Figure 21 Topic/Post user modal

Home / Categories

Instructions Delete

Here you can find instructions about the the Knowledge Exchange Platform

3D Models Delete

Here you can find the 3D models used in our project

Tutorials Delete

Here you can find tutorials and instruction on how to use them

Manuals Delete

Here you can find manuals and instructions

New category

Figure 22 Administration privileges (e.g. "Delete" options)

Lastly, administrators launching the KEP have the ability to edit or even delete categories, topics and posts made by others and reorganize the whole structure of the forum. The administration tool provides an easy and intuitive way to manage the platform. It also includes monitoring tools to always be in control of the platform's status. In this way, a more direct interaction can be achieved and the whole platform can easily be customized towards industrial needs and working convenience.

Deployment of KEP in Ageing@Work's server

Regarding the deployment of our Knowledge Exchange Platform, the last step was to migrate our cloud database to Ageing@Work's public IP for maintenance reasons and to start the piloting phase.

Docker was chosen for this procedure, and the whole collection of data stored in our database in the cloud was transferred to CERTH's premises to be deployed in the public IP. Docker is an open-source containerization platform that enables developers to package applications into virtual containers. These isolated executable components combine source code with the operating system (OS), libraries and dependencies required from our application in order to run that code in any environment, excluding any prior installation or configuration. This makes it easier to modify and update the whole structure and thus making the application portable in a repeatable way.

As a result, a single command would be enough to run our whole platform under any environment, making the migration process fast and efficient.

4.2.1 VR/AR lifelong learning tools

A set of lifelong learning tools in virtual reality was developed (and reported in D6.2) in order to provide an immersive environment that allows one to experience the process of teaching or learning as a game. These tools include the *XR tutorial creation module*, which gives the opportunity to an experienced worker to create and record a tutorial with certain steps related to a specific procedure, and the *XR tutorial execution module*, through which a novice worker can enter the virtual environment and get trained following the steps shown in the recorded tutorial. The illustrated tutorial steps, indications and visual hints are adapted to the chosen "difficulty" level, similarly as in computer games where the user progresses into levels according to his/her experience and achieved tasks. Both modules share common VR/XR-based technological tools mainly targeting the interaction of a real user with objects in a modeled 3D scene. Their development is based on Unity3D which facilitates the design of interactive XR training scenarios.

In this section, after a small description of the different modules, we will focus on I/O integration aspects, i.e. (i) present the front ends developed for the usage of the VR lifelong learning tools by instructors or trainees and (ii) describe the integration with the KEP to facilitate knowledge sharing (transfer and retrieval of the created tutorial files) by any worker with Aging@Work account. More details can be found in the deliverable D6.2. and in <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Odf0oA7x5d8>

XR Tutorial Creation Module: The XR tutorial creation module is used to create a training tutorial in order to educate inexperienced workers on the use of machines or industrial control panels in simple or more complex scenarios, avoiding dangers and risks inherent during the real (physical) job assignments. It utilizes a set of XR tools designed to simplify the process of creating or editing training tutorials.

The XR tutorial creation module is initiated by first loading a previously designed 3D workplace of interest. Depending on the device the user can interact with objects of the environment using his bare hands or the controllers, as described above. Every 3D interaction is tracked automatically and marked as a new step of the training tutorial. If the user makes a mistake through the process, he/she can delete the tracked step through the 2D panel appearing in front of him/her. When all the steps are completed, the user presses the (virtual) save button, and the Tutorial Manager encodes the tutorial in a JSON formatted file.

XR Tutorial Execution Module: The XR tutorial execution module allows to rollout previously developed training programs, i.e., JSON encoded tutorials. The module includes the same components

with the XR tutorial creation module, i.e., interactable components, machine components, trackable components, and a Tutorial Manager, although their utilization is different. The Tutorial Manager operates as an intermediate control mechanism for both modules. The identification of a step as correct is based on the common information shared between the machine component and the tutorial manager. The interactions currently supported by the framework are simple and can result in categorical states with two or more categories or continuous-valued states (e.g., rotation angle of a handle).

A 2D visualization panel projected in the users' front view is also utilized here to guide the trainee through the process by illustrating the sequence of performed and required actions and by displaying his/her performance after each execution task. The user gets notified through the panel so that he/she can proceed to the next step. Moreover, to facilitate novice trainees, several types of indications are available in this module; i.e., every interaction is visualized on the (unfamiliar) machine by highlights in non-moving parts and animation in dynamic parts.

Front-ends and functionality of main menu

For the purposes of an easy and intuitive navigation of the user inside our framework, we developed a main menu scene, through which the user can proceed on setting up the desired environment. First of all, the user is presented with the option to select between online and offline functionality (Figure 23).

Online functionality: If the “Continue offline” option is **not** selected, the worker will be asked to type his credentials with the help of a virtual keyboard, as a means to login to the Knowledge Exchange Platform (described in section 4.2.4) designed for knowledge sharing. If the credentials are correct, the user logs in successfully and obtains the respective session cookie, which will enable free navigation through the platform, from the personal account and proceed with the desired interactions. This cookie will be his identity while he is connected to the forum. An example of the set of possible actions that can take place, is the creation of a post in the forum or the download of a stored tutorial regarding the use of a specific tool/machine. Otherwise, in the case of providing wrong logging credentials, an error message will be shown, to inform the user that he/she needs to proceed on reinserting them.

Offline functionality: In the case that “Continue offline” is selected, the user will continue her/his navigation to our framework offline. This means that when s/he creates a tutorial, the tutorial will be saved locally at his personal computer and it will not be uploaded to KEP. Additionally, if s/he chooses to get trained, the available tutorials will be the ones which are saved to that computer.

Figure 23 Main Menu: Login Panel

After logging in or continuing offline, a choice is provided to the worker to select the virtual environment he/she wants to load, among the available ones, as shown in Figure 24

Figure 24 Main Menu: Virtual Environment selection

The navigation continues with the mode selection. Here, the user is given 3 choices (Figure 25):

- **Build Mode** to create a tutorial for a novice worker by navigating in the selected virtual environment and recording the steps for a certain procedure,
- **Train Mode** for inexperienced workers or beginners, who want to get trained,
- **Free Play Mode** for both novice and experienced workers, who want to enter the selected virtual environment to get familiar with all the interactions that have been created.

Figure 25 Main Menu: Mode Selection

If the “train” mode is selected, then the user will be asked to choose the tutorial he wants to follow. There will be a list of the available tutorials on the left of the panel (Figure 25). An option to choose the difficulty level of the training is also provided, which determines the visual hints (steps description) and interaction’s indications that will be visible to the trainee.

Figure 26 Main Menu: Tutorial and Difficulty level selection

In easy mode, both steps description and interaction indications are provided. In medium difficulty, interaction indication is disabled and, finally, in the hard version of the training all hints for visual guidance are hidden.

Knowledge sharing and retrieval through the KEP

The knowledge transfer procedure is a vital component of the overall interaction between the VR platform and the KEP framework. Both high- and low-level detail is important to be highlighted in order to fully comprehend both the technical aspects and the importance of that functionality. When addressing the low level information about the data exchange procedures that take place, three major operations are available to the user from the VR platform:

- User Login
- Viewing/Downloading saved Tutorials
- Uploading Tutorials

In the KEP platform and the VR experience there is a respective login option which is aiming to be a part of a universal login profile which can be used in multiple components across the entire solution. This profile will contain different kinds of data (anthropometric, personal) and will be used as a universal account/key to access the different functionalities of the entire structure. As a result, the re-insertion of the credentials in the current version in both the VR experience and KEP platform, though it may seem redundant, is more focused on providing the greater picture of navigating between different components by a single profile while also ensuring security. For the login functionality, in order to validate the user in the VR platform (either experience or novice one), a login form is being presented as a first step. In order to proceed, the user needs to insert his/her credentials by a VR keyboard. In case of an unsuccessful response, the user is required to reenter the credentials. In case of a successful response, a token, generated from the KEP platform, is being saved along with his username inside the Unity3D's framework, in order to be retrieved whenever needed (e.g. when uploading a tutorial).

Regarding the knowledge sharing procedure, all available uploaded tutorials can be retrieved anytime, and automatically parsed by a GET operation from the XR platform, which takes place when the user (trainee) selects the train option. The GET operation proceeds on, initially, storing the name of the tutorial (e.g. DrillingMachineTutorial) and the selected training options step information (Figure 28). By choosing a specific tutorial, the steps are being rendered in the next scene's panel (Figure 27).

The tutorial file recorded by an instructor (experienced worker) can be uploaded to the KEP, in a JSON format. The content of the JSON format is shown in the example in Figure 28 and fundamentally, apart from including relevant integration - wise information (*Command Id*) is mentioning every command - required step to complete the tutorial (e.g. "*Command Description*" : "*Open the protection fuse.*")

```
[{"InteractableGuid":{"value":"d6a3ef6e-5996-4e73-8203-081b386f9450"},
"MachineGuid":{"value":"bf564476-d776-493f-931a-59fdaacc7e60"},
"Commandstate":1.0,"CommandId":5,"CommandDescription":"open the protection fuse."},
{"InteractableGuid":{"value":"18814d95-aa8c-4276-ae30-2c237c70f988"},
"MachineGuid":{"value":"bf564476-d776-493f-931a-59fdaacc7e60"},"Commandstate":1.0,
"CommandId":12,"CommandDescription":"clamp the Metal Piece on the drill area."},
```

Figure 27 Example of a recorded tutorial in JSON format

During the GET operation from the VR platform, a custom - made parser has been developed in order to retrieve the steps of each uploaded tutorial in the given section. As a result, for each pair of sets, the JSON format is being read from the parser and through byte format, being transferred to the VR environment where the information is being encoded once again into a JSON file in order to be processed and thus, displayed to the respective panel in Unity (Figure 28)).

Figure 28 Steps in Train Mode

Regarding the POST operation, i.e. the procedure of uploading tutorials in the KEP through the XR framework, the user after recording the desired set of steps, by hitting the save button, initiates the decoding of the JSON format of the steps and the creation of a specific web form, easily readable from the REST API service which is deployed and operating in the KEP platform. In that service, a method has been developed whereby by acquiring specific ids for a topic and category and by combining the user's credential is able to transfer and upload the information in a json format to the platform.

Entering the chosen virtual Environment / Application example of the XR framework

Here, we present an application example of the XR framework. By selecting the “train” mode, the user enters the virtual environment in order to create a training scenario and record all necessary steps that his workers need to follow and execute. For our case, the training scenario describes the steps required for the operation of an industrial drilling machine. The training tutorial includes actions for safety assurance for the machine and the worker, as well as operation instructions of drilling a hole in an object of a certain material. It consists of the following 13 specific steps:

1. Press the emergency button to ensure that the machine is off.
2. Open the protection glass.
3. Insert the drill bit.
4. Close the protection glass.
5. Grab the object and insert it under the drill.
6. Open the fuse to unlock height adjustment.
7. Adjust height with the top lever.
8. Close the fuse to lock height adjustment.
9. Wear the protection goggles.
10. Open the cap of the emergency button.
11. Turn the machine on by pressing the green button.
12. Drill a hole into the object by pulling the drilling adjustment lever.
13. Turn the machine off by pressing the red button.

The proposed scenario requires the 3D modeling and visualization of the drilling machine, the drill bit, the protective glasses and the 3D work space environment.

Figure 29 demonstrates the overall view, some steps of the tutorial creation process and their illustration in the 2D panel, in the case of the “build” mode selection. Some steps of the tutorial execution process (“train” mode selection), indicated in the 2D panel as successfully completed or pending, are demonstrated in Figure 29

Figure 29 The overall view of the virtual workspace, some of the tutorial steps followed and the final result in the 2D panel

Figure 30 Some of the steps followed in the tutorial execution mode alongside with the animation and highlight indications.

4.3 Job scheduling tools

4.3.1 General architecture

This component aims to provide tools to managers to better optimize the tasks of the ageing workers. The high-level architecture is shown in the following figure.

Figure 31 Architecture of the job scheduling tools

4.3.2 Management dashboard

The Aging@Work Management dashboard is the main tool which offers organization managers a detailed overview of the workforce, task assignments and shift schedule. In addition, it allows managers to make interventions on the facility schedule, which are fully DSS supported, as well as react to worker requests.

From the user standpoint, the Management Dashboard comprises a web interface with a number of discrete specialized views, as well as a main overview screen. The overview screen offers a comprehensive outline of the weekly workforce task and shift assignments and enables the manager to hover over the view for additional details.

From a development standpoint, the Management dashboard is a web app based on MySQL, PHP, Laravel and Angular.js, which comprises the following main components:

- A MySQL store for schedule-related data storage and
- An API implemented using OpenAPI, which enables aggregation of schedule and shift-related data and retrieval for presentation
- A frontend based on Angular.js, which implements the required views for Manager dashboard functionality.

The Management Dashboard is deployed via a standard Composer-based deployment procedure. Composer is the standard package management system used in the Laravel framework. The requirements for the Manager dashboard are a LAMP setup and Composer installation.

The subcomponents of the Management dashboard have undergone functional testing using standardized API calls through Postman. The overall integrated system has undergone basic usability testing, and additional testing scenarios are planned to be implemented as necessary during the project integration phase. A video demonstrator is available at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=WX3l-2scclmI>.

Figure 32 Ageing@WorkManager Dashboard showing the weekly shift assignments view

4.3.3 Participatory Work orchestration tool

Scheduling of human resources is an important activity undertaken by management in a daily basis to maintain full functionality of industrial operations. Scheduling is a highly complex activity that comprises multiple decision variables, objectives and constraints. As such, it is of paramount importance that decision makers such as managers are supported by intelligent computational decision support systems, so as informed design decisions are performed, that promote efficiency while respecting health and safety regulations and personal preferences of the workforce. This has even greater importance in the case of ageing workers which potentially have increased requirements with respect to looking after their health and well-being, but also because the ageing workforce is a carrier of much of the organization’s knowledge that is required in day-to-day operations.

The Participatory Work Orchestration tool facilitates the orchestration of the organization workforce, through its main function which is to provide decision support for shift management, in accordance with organization policies, worker preferences and occupational standards. The tool comprises the following main parts:

- The job scheduling algorithmic core, which is a service that receives a job scheduling context, which comprises details regarding the workforce, the tasks to be performed, the defined shifts, worker preferences and individual OSH and health-related parameters, performs the actual shift scheduling/optimization, and returns the results. The module runs on-prem, and does not have any remote service dependencies, thus any data received is maintained on the organization

premises. Any data received is only utilized for the course of computation and is then discarded. In addition, it is possible to fully anonymize data prior to input.

- The job scheduling backend, which is part of the management dashboard backend, and which stores the derived schedules so that they are available at any time to managers and to individual workers (which may only access their own schedules). This includes the necessary API for the front-end to access the stored data.
- The schedule controller, views and related functionality, which is part of the Manager Platform front-end. This module comprises a series of views that offer a comprehensive overview of the current shift schedule, as well as task assignments of the workforce. In addition, it offers ancillary views that enable managers to view and respond to worker requests.

The Participatory Work Orchestration tools has undergone a series of tests. First, the job scheduling algorithmic core has undergone functional and performance tests, to ensure both that required input/output pairs are validated, as well as to validate performance against given targets. The implementations is in Python 3.x and testing has been performed using the unittest framework. In addition, the backend and API has been tested using standardized API calls using Postman.

4.4 Other components

4.4.1 Reward system

The reward system aims to use gamification techniques to improve the adherence of the Ageing@Work system of the users. Both, managers and workers can benefit from the motivational elements to improve health, workability and improve the adherence to the intervention and proposed solutions. More information of the system is in the D5.2, as well as the validation and integration aspects of this component that finally was not integrated in the use cases presented in this deliverable.

4.4.2 Ergonomic optimization support tool

In this section, the integration of the Ergonomic Optimization Support Tool (EOST) is briefly described. The tool itself is developed in T3.4, and a full explanation of the tool itself will be available in deliverable D3.3. The main goal of the EOST is to provide the workers with an ergonomics simulation tool to assess their workplace compatibility with them and inform the worker of the best way to setup their workplace (like chair height) to improve their productivity, health and comfort, and informing the worker of any potential health problems (like back pain) that might arise or worsen while performing work. The Demonstrator video is available in <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=QrUW5Cbad8I>

EOST inputs and outputs

This section includes the list of inputs and outputs of the tool, so the rest of the explanations are understood more easily.

Inputs

- Workplace characteristics: This is the type of workplace itself (i.e., desk with computer, drilling machine), along with the possibilities when configuring the workplace (i.e., for the desk with computer, the minimum and maximum chair height)
- Worker model: This is all the information about the worker's anthropometric characteristics (i.e., the user's height, or the length of their forearm)

Outputs

- Workplace configuration: This is a specific configuration of the workplace (i.e., a specific chair height). For all characteristics, the configuration should fall inside the valid ranges.
- Workplace setup score: This is an overall score of the user workability in the workplace with a specific configuration. Different workplace configurations for the same user will result in different scores. The higher the score, the better.
- Potential problems: This is a list of all the potential problems that might happen with a specific worker, workplace and workplace configuration.

EOST user workflow

The user interfaces with the tool from the Worker Dashboard from the mobile phone application as it was explained previously (section 4.1.2). To start, the users must go to the ergonomics section, and select which of the available workplaces they work at. Here a more detailed explanation of the EOST workflow is explaining complementing the previously reported information in Dashboard section.

Depending on the workplace, the user might need to specify the workplace characteristics. For workplaces that are performed in the company site, this is not needed, as these characteristics are already known through the workplace virtual model in the Ageing@Work Central Repository, but for unknown workplaces, like working from home, the user needs to input the data so the system can do the simulation. Optionally, the user can input one or more specific workplace configurations, so their reports are also generated, even if a more optimal configuration is found.

Once setup, this information is sent to the tool and the user does not need to interface with the system anymore. The tool performs all the calculations in the background, and, once complete, the information will be available back for the user.

Once the calculations are complete, the user can go back to the ergonomics section and review their results. The results include the optimal configuration of the workplace that the tool calculated, along with an overall score and a list of potential problems that might arise when working.

If any specific workplace configurations were set up, their results will also be displayed, so that they can compare them with the optimal. This allows the worker to check if their preferred or more comfortable configuration has any potential problem, to allow them to continue working as they were used to.

EOST architecture

The ergonomics tool is composed of six different parts:

- REST API: Communicates with the rest of the system

- Storage: Stores data to be processed and ergonomics reports
- Queuing: Starts processing of workplaces on a queue so they are all analyzed
- Simulation: Runs the simulation of the worker in the workplace
- Analysis: Analyses the simulation to generate a score and report problems
- Optimization: Finds the optimal workplace configuration by using the simulation and analysis parts

Figure 33 Architecture of the ergonomic orchestrator

5. Conclusions

The Ageing@Work system follows a combined approach to provide the whole functionalities described in the architecture. Three main demonstrators have been prepared to demonstrate the feasibility and usefulness of the envisioned functionalities: Worker application, aimed to support worker to adopt and maintain healthy habits both at work and in their private life, AR/VR tools and Knowledge Exchange Platform aimed to provide tools to worker to acquire new knowledge and skills and Job Scheduling tools aimed to support managers in a better aged workforce management.

These three demonstrators exchange data and services using the Ageing@Work Central Repository, that thanks to the developed REST API, the integration of the different components was successfully implemented ..